

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/pocock2012
hash://md5/87aa6e54b11f6fade5504d82152a3ddd

by Nomer, Elton and Preston, three naive review bots
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<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/pocock2012/issues>

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/pocock2012, has fingerprint hash://md5/87aa6e54b11f6fade5504d82152a3ddd, is 142KiB in size and contains 1,148 interactions with 3 unique types of associations (e.g., eats) between 315 primary taxa (e.g., *Fringilla coelebs*) and 95 associated taxa (e.g., *Ranunculus repens*). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

Contents

Introduction	2
Data Review and Archive	2
Methods	2
Results	4
Files	4
Archived Dataset	14
Biotic Interactions	14

Interaction Networks	18
Geospatial Distribution	19
Taxonomic Alignment	19
Additional Reviews	24
GloBI Review Badge	24
GloBI Index Badge	24
Discussion	25
Acknowledgements	25
Author contributions	26
References	26

Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Pocock, Michael J. O.; Evans, Darren M.; Memmott, Jane (2012),
 Data from: The robustness and restoration of a network of ecological
 networks, Dryad, Dataset, <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.3s36r118>
<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/pocock2012/archive/be57f1d26a208fb4b2adfad72e17a3b88a2026-01-24T05:45:36.799Z> hash://md5/87aa6e54b11f6fade5504d82152a3ddd

For additional metadata related to this dataset, please visit <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/pocock2012> and inspect associated metadata files including, but not limited to, *README.md*, *eml.xml*, and/or *globi.json*.

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.4
nomer	0.5.17
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 142KiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/pocock2012

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/pocock2012\
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/pocock2012\
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/pocock2012\
| nomer append col\
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](#). See also [GitHub](#) and [Codeberg](#).

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/pocock2012`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/pocock2012`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/pocock2012`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/pocock2012`)

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format

filename	description
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/pocock2012`, has fingerprint hash://md5/87aa6e54b11f6fade5504d82152a3ddd, is 142KiB in size and contains 1,148 interactions with 3 unique types of associations (e.g., eats) between 315 primary taxa (e.g., *Fringilla coelebs*) and 95 associated taxa (e.g., *Ranunculus repens*).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 3: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Rhingia campestris	visitsFlowersOf	Ajuga reptans	Pocock, Michael J. O.; Evans, Darren M.; Memmott, Jane (2012), Data from: The robustness and restoration of a network of ecological networks, Dryad, Dataset, https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.3s36r118 . Accessed at https://datadryad.org/stash/downloads/file_stream/40321 on 29 Jan 2026.
Simulium sp	visitsFlowersOf	Alliaria petiolata	Pocock, Michael J. O.; Evans, Darren M.; Memmott, Jane (2012), Data from: The robustness and restoration of a network of ecological networks, Dryad, Dataset, https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.3s36r118 . Accessed at https://datadryad.org/stash/downloads/file_stream/40321 on 29 Jan 2026.

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Agriotes pallidulus	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	Pocock, Michael J. O.; Evans, Darren M.; Memmott, Jane (2012), Data from: The robustness and restoration of a network of ecological networks, Dryad, Dataset, https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.3s36r118 . Accessed at https://datadryad.org/stash/downloads/file_stream/40321 on 29 Jan 2026.
Anaspis maculata	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	Pocock, Michael J. O.; Evans, Darren M.; Memmott, Jane (2012), Data from: The robustness and restoration of a network of ecological networks, Dryad, Dataset, https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.3s36r118 . Accessed at https://datadryad.org/stash/downloads/file_stream/40321 on 29 Jan 2026.

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
eats	532
visitsFlowersOf	501
visits	115

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Fringilla coelebs	52
Carduelis chloris	51
Alectoris rufa	49
Carduelis cannabina	47
Carduelis carduelis	44
Passer domesticus	39
Columba palumbus	37
Corvus frugilegus	34
Emberiza citrinella	34
Apodemus sylvaticus	31
Corvus monedula	23
Empis livida	22
Myodes glareolus	22
Alauda arvensis	15
Platycheirus albimanus	14
Apodemus flavicollis	14
Pegoplata aestiva or Adia cinerella	13
Scathophaga stercoraria	12
Micromys minutus	11

Table 6: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Ranunculus repens	92
Cirsium arvense	66
Rubus fruticosus	60
Matricaria recutita	59
Trifolium pratense/repens	57

targetTaxonName	count
Heracleum sphondylium	53
Anthriscus sylvestris	47
Cirsium vulgare	33
Sinapis arvensis	29
Crataegus monogyna	26
Senecio jacobaea	23
Torilis japonica	22
Poaceae	20
Rumex sp.	17
Leontodon autumnalis	16
Rosa sp.	15
Chenopodium sp.	15
Cerastium fontanum	14
Sonchus asper/oleraceus	14

Table 7: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Rhingia campestris	visitsFlowersOf	Ajuga reptans	1
Simulium sp	visitsFlowersOf	Alliaria petiolata	1
Agriotes pallidulus	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Anaspis maculata	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Anthocomus fasciatus	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Bicellaria vana	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Botanophila striolata	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Bracon sp	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Cantharis lateralis	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Chlorops hypostigma	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Chlorops pumilionis	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Dacnusa (maculipes)	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Delia sp	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Dicraeus tibialis	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Dolichopus unguatus	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Empis (Xanthempis) sp	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Empis caudatula	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Empis livida	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1
Empis nigripes	visitsFlowersOf	Anthriscus sylvestris	1

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows

how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download [svg](#)

You can download the indexed dataset under review at [indexed-interactions.csv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at [indexed-interactions.gpkg](#) for point data and [indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg](#) for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at [GloBI website](#), by opening a [GitHub issue](#), or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the [GloBI website](#).

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., [col](#), [ncbi](#), [discoverlife](#), [gbif](#), [itis](#), [wfo](#), [mdd](#), [tpt](#), [pbdb](#), and [worms](#)). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 8: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Acer campestre	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Acer campestre
Acer pseudoplatanus	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Acer pseudoplatanus
Acyrtosiphon pisum	SYNONYM_OF	col	Acyrtosiphon primulae

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Acyrthosiphon pisum	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Acyrthosiphon pisum

Table 9: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	87
col	family	9
col	genus	44
col	order	1
col	species	266
col	subgenus	2
col	subspecies	15
discoverlife	NA	397
discoverlife	species	11
gbif	NA	34
gbif	family	10
gbif	genus	50
gbif	order	1
gbif	species	316
gbif	subspecies	14
itis	NA	178
itis	family	9
itis	genus	41
itis	order	1
itis	species	177
itis	subfamily	1
itis	subspecies	1
mdd	NA	408
ncbi	NA	52
ncbi	family	9
ncbi	genus	43
ncbi	order	1
ncbi	species	298
ncbi	subfamily	2
ncbi	subgenus	3
ncbi	tribe	1
ncbi	varietas	1
pbdb	NA	348
pbdb	family	9

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
pbdb	genus	24
pbdb	order	1
pbdb	species	23
pbdb	subfamily	2
pbdb	tribe	1
tpt	NA	394
tpt	species	14
wfo	NA	324
wfo	family	1
wfo	genus	10
wfo	species	73
wfo	subspecies	1
worms	NA	307
worms	family	8
worms	genus	27
worms	order	1
worms	species	65

Table 10: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	297
col	SYNONYM_OF	159
col	NONE	87
discoverlife	NONE	399
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	11
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	1
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	411
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	154
gbif	NONE	34
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	216
itis	NONE	179
itis	SYNONYM_OF	18
mdd	NONE	407
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	3
ncbi	SAME_AS	339

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	21
ncbi	NONE	52
pdb	NONE	349
pdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	58
pdb	SYNONYM_OF	3
tpt	NONE	396
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	14
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	81
wfo	NONE	326
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	10
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	22
worms	NONE	308
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	96
worms	SYNONYM_OF	13

Table 11: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 12: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-01-28T23:34:09Z	summary	https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/pocock201
2026-01-28T23:34:09Z	summary	1148 interaction(s)
2026-01-28T23:34:09Z	summary	0 note(s)
2026-01-28T23:34:09Z	summary	1734 info(s)

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

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⁵At time of writing (2026-01-29) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

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